

Modelling and Assessing the Risk of Cascading Effects with ResilBlockly

Irene Bicchierai
ResilTech S.R.L.
Pontedera (PI), Italy
irene.bicchierai@resiltech.com

Enrico Schiavone
ResilTech S.R.L.
Pontedera (PI), Italy
enrico.schiavone@resiltech.com

Francesco Brancati
ResilTech S.R.L.
Pontedera (PI), Italy
francesco.brancati@resiltech.com

Abstract— **Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) is an expanding research area that involves preventing cascading effects within and between Critical Infrastructures (CIs). A cascading effect occurs when one CI affects another, usually negatively, through dependencies between them. In this paper, we present the adoption of a methodology for the analysis of cascading effects in critical infrastructures, its implementation in a MDE tool, ResilBlockly, and its application to the protection of ground segment of space systems in the context of a European project.**

Keywords—*Critical Infrastructure, Model-Driven Engineering, security assessment, cascading effects, ground segment of space systems*

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of *cascading events* is defined in relation to disasters and/or emergency management as “events that occur as a direct or indirect result of an initial event” [3]. In [2], *cascading effects* are defined as “the dynamics present in disasters, in which the impact of a physical event or the development of an initial technological or human failure, generates a sequence of events in human subsystems that result in physical, social or economic disruption”.

A cascading effect occurs when a failure on a critical infrastructure affects another, usually negatively, because they are dependent from each other. For example, a water supply system could start to have problems after a failure in the power supply system, because the pumps depend on electricity.

The integration of CIs and their combined use provide advantages in terms of efficiency, quality of service and cost reduction, but the interdependencies increase the vulnerability of the infrastructure as there are greater channels for propagating errors from an infrastructure to other and therefore the increased exposure to accidental and malicious threats. This means that the impact of infrastructure component failures and their severity can be aggravated, higher and more difficult to estimate, than failures limited to one single infrastructure. Hence, cascading effects in interconnected infrastructures can lead to catastrophic events, as they affect more infrastructures which can also cover large geographical areas.

The risk assessment cannot be performed considering single risk indices correlated to independent events, since the overall risk index from a sequence of risks may exceed the simple aggregation of single risk ratios. Hence the multi-risk assessment should be performed taking into account all possible interactions of risks due to cascading effects, thus heavily increasing the complexity of the analysis.

Assessing the risk of cascading effects in CIs that are inherently complex, requires to consider all the several possible interactions that may emerge, and this is clearly an activity that cannot be performed, with a reasonably low cognitive complexity, without the support of an ad-hoc software tool.

II. RELATED WORKS

Over the years, several methods and tools have been designed and developed for the analysis of cascading effects. These methods can be divided into four groups: empirical, economic-based, agent-based and system dynamic-based.

In Empirical approaches, special databases from the incident reports are established and then the data is analysed to identify frequent and significant failure patterns. Relevant information, such the quantification of interdependency related indicators, the types of CIs that most frequently damage other CIs, the relationship between being a cause of failure and being affected by failure, are calculated from collected fault data. The article [4] presents a set of empirical functions to examine cyber interdependencies for different critical infrastructures. Some researchers, as the authors of [8], [5], [6] and [7], have studied the cascading effects produced by natural events e.g., blackout, ice storm, hurricanes, earthquakes.

In Agent-based approaches, most CIs components can be viewed as agents. These approaches are used to model CIs interdependencies and are mainly adopted by national laboratories: Aspen [9] simulates the behaviours of economic decision-makers in U.S. economy; Aspen-EE [10] is the Aspen extended to simulate the interdependent effects of power market adjustment and power outages on other CIs; the Critical Infrastructure Modelling System (CIMS) [1] tool, is developed by Idaho to analyse the cascading effects and consequences associated with CIs interdependencies through a graphical (3D) representation of CIs component and the associated relationships.

System dynamics-based approaches use top-down approaches to analyse complex adaptive systems that involve interdependencies. Their fundamental concepts are feedback loops that indicate the connection and direction of effects between CIs components; stocks, representing quantities or states of the system; flow rates between stocks that controlled their levels overtime. Two European projects adopted this approach: FORTRESS [11] and CascEff [12]. The first involves the use of two user friendly tools: the FORTRESS Model builder (FMB) and the FORTRESS Incident Evolution Tool (FIET). The FMB is a tool for modelling dependencies and relationships between systems and stakeholders in crisis scenarios, the FIET offers a set of tools to analyse how a crisis

scenario might evolve. Two tools are used in CascEff: An Incident Evolution Methodology to understand and model cascading effects, and an Incident Evolution Tool to perform simulations of cascading effects as a result of an initiating event.

In Economic Theory-based Approaches the interdependencies of CIs can be analysed through models of economic interdependencies. In [13], a static and linear model of all purchases and sales between sectors of an economy is presented.

Network-based approaches model CIs as networks where the components of CIs are nodes and the physical connections are links. These approaches describe the interdependencies by inter-links, their topologies and flow patterns. There are many network-based studies, as [15] and [14], while [16] proposes a mixed network-based and empirical method. Some improvements of this algorithm have been introduced over the years as shown by [17] and [18]. To our knowledge, no software tool is available that allows to easily model complex CIs and analyse their risk of cascading effect based on this approach.

III. ADOPTED METHODOLOGY FOR THE ANALYSIS OF CASCADING EFFECTS

The chosen method is based on the mixed network-based and empirical method presented in [16] and on the subsequent improvements introduced in [17], [18]. It can be summarized in the following steps: assets and dependencies definitions; multi-risk dependency analysis centrality metrics, nodes and higher-risk paths analysis.

A. Asset and dependency definitions

For each identified dependency, it is useful to define the initiating asset, the cascading asset, the type of dependency, threat or failure mode, the impact or the effect, the severity, the likelihood and the risk associated. At this point, it is possible to construct a table as Table 1.

TABLE 1. FIRST-ORDER DEPENDENCIES TABLE

Init. Asset	Casc. Asset	Dependency Type(s)	Impact Scale $I_{i,j}$	Likelihood $L_{i,j}$	Risk $R_{i,j}$ [0-10]
A_1	A_2	Service Cyber	Low	Low	3
...					

The method employs a graph to model the dependencies between the assets; in particular, each asset is represented as a node, while each dependency is represented as a link. It is therefore possible to define a graph $G = (N, E)$, where N is the set of nodes (assets) and E is the set of edges (dependencies). The graph is directional so as to show the dependencies between one node and another.

A link between node A_i and node A_j , i.e., $A_i \rightarrow A_j$, implies a risk relation of node A_j from node A_i . A bi-directional arrow $A_i \leftrightarrow A_j$ denotes a cascading risk from A_i to A_j and another cascading risk from A_j to A_i . This relation needs to be associated with the impact $I_{i,j}$ and the likelihood $L_{i,j}$ of a disturbance occurrence. The likelihood value set is assigned as

follows: $VL = [0-0.05]$, $L = (0.05-0.25)$, $M = (0.25-0.5)$, $H = (0.5-0.75)$ and $VH = (0.75-1)$. Impact values follow NIST guidelines [25] and are as follows: $VH = 10$, $H = 8$, $M = 5$, $L = 2$ and $VL = 0$. The product of these two values allows to evaluate the dependency risk $R_{i,j}$ to asset A_j due to its dependence on asset A_i .

Each edge of the graph is associated with a numerical value which ascribes the level of the cascade-resulting risk for the receiver due to the dependency. A risk scale [0 to 10], where 10 is the most rigorous risk, is used to depict this risk. All the parameters ($L_{i,j}$, $I_{i,j}$, $R_{i,j}$) are defined in order to assess the risk of first-order dependencies.

B. Multi-risk dependency analysis

Once the dependencies of the first order have been analysed with the method described above, it is possible to evaluate the potential risks of the n th order using a recursive algorithm. The algorithm examines each critical asset A_{Y_0} as a potential cause of a cascading chain and then it computes the dependency risk DR exhibited by A_{Y_n} due to its n th-order dependency.

Let $A = (A_1, \dots, A_m)$ be the set of assets, $A_{Y_0} \rightarrow A_{Y_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow A_{Y_n}$ denoting a chain of assets dependencies of length n , L_{Y_0, \dots, Y_n} be the likelihood of an n th-order cascading event and I_{Y_{n-1}, Y_n} be the impact of the $A_{Y_{n-1}} \rightarrow A_{Y_n}$ dependency. The cascading risk exhibited by A_{Y_n} due to the n th-order dependency can be evaluated by following (1).

$$R_{Y_0, \dots, Y_n} = L_{Y_0, \dots, Y_n} \cdot I_{Y_{n-1}, Y_n} \equiv \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} L_{Y_i, Y_{i+1}} \cdot I_{Y_{n-1}, Y_n}$$

The cumulative dependency risk accounts for the overall risk exhibited by all assets in the sub-chains of the n -th order of dependency.

Let $A_{Y_0} \rightarrow A_{Y_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow A_{Y_n}$ be a chain of dependencies of length n . The cumulative dependency risk, denoted as $CR_{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_n}$ is defined as the overall risk produced by an n th-order dependency and is computed as:

$$CR_{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_n} = \sum_{i=1}^n R_{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_i} \equiv \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\prod_{j=1}^i L_{Y_{j-1}, Y_j} \right) \cdot I_{Y_{i-1}, Y_i} \quad (2)$$

In order to achieve the product of the likelihood, a standard matrix can be used.

Equation (2) calculates the cumulative dependency risk exposed by each node in the chain due to a realized failure in the source of the dependency chain. The risk calculation is based on a risk matrix that combines the probability and the input impact values of each vertex in the chain. More details can be found in [16]. It can be made the assumption that if a node fails, then also the dependent nodes will fail (likelihood equal to 1), thus obtaining the result of (3).

$$CR_{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_n} = \sum_{i=1}^n R_{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_i} \equiv \sum_{i=1}^n I_{Y_{i-1}, Y_i} \quad (3)$$

The method computes the graph's overall risk, GR, as the sum of the cumulative dependency risk for each nth-order dependency in the graph using the total number of all asset sub-chains and their cumulative dependency risks as shown in (4)

$$GR = \sum CR \quad (4)$$

The analysis performed by means of (1) and (2) provides an assessment of the overall risk related to the occurrence of a single initiating event that then triggers cascading effects. To capture the overall risk of the occurrence of a failure that affects multiple critical infrastructures, and potentially initiates multiple cascading effects, it is necessary to perform an analysis that accounts for these complex situations. A few steps are taken to achieve this goal as in [16]. In particular, the so-called Common Cause Threat is first identified, i.e., all potential Tx threats that may result in a common cause failure in a critical infrastructure. At this point, it is important to associate a likelihood to each threat. A worst-case approach is typically used, as a result of a worst-case risk assessment. For each initiating event, (2) is used to assess the nth order dependency risk for every critical infrastructure that is initially affected by the common-cause threat. Finally, the combined common-cause and cascading failure risk is assessed as follows.

Let A be the set of all examined Critical Infrastructures. The combined risk of all possible cascading event chains $A_{Y_0} \rightarrow A_{Y_1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow A_{Y_n}$ for each possible source infrastructure $A_{Y_0} \in A$ is calculated as the sum of all possible risk chains $CR_{Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_n}$ for all $Y_0 \in A$ multiplied by the probability L_{Tx}

$$\sum CR_{Y_0, \dots, Y_n}(T_x) = L_{Tx} \cdot \sum_{\forall Y_0 \in A} CR_{Y_0, \dots, Y_n} \quad (5)$$

Equation 5 combines the likelihood L_{Tx} of a threat Tx with all possible dependency chains that could arise once the threat occurs or is realized. It examines each critical infrastructure that is affected by Tx as a possible root dependency chain based on the risk dependency table and dependency graph.

C. Centrality metrics, nodes and higher-risk paths analysis

To better conduct the analysis, it is useful to highlight the most critical nodes, i.e., those nodes whose failure would affect many other nodes, causing a series of cascading effects with all the damage that would result. Once the most critical nodes are highlighted, it is possible to operate by taking countermeasures to limit the effects.

This type of analysis is performed using metrics of centrality on the graphs. In this way, it is quantified the position of a node in relation to others and is estimated the relative importance within the graph. Nodes that have a high centrality denote a great influence on the entire graph; for this reason, they represent good candidates to perform risk mitigation controls in order to minimize the occurrence of cascading effects.

IV. RESILBLOCKLY

A. Architecture

This section introduces technologies and methods behind ResilBlockly, a software tool that evolves Blockly4SoS, a

prototype tool developed in the context of AMADEOS [19] project as solution for reducing the cognitive complexity required for modelling Systems-of-Systems (SoS). Such evolution has been devised in order to support not only the modelling of the main SoS concepts, but also to perform hazard analysis, to enable threats modelling, and to address the assessment of risk resulting from the cascading effect.

From the functional point of view, ResilBlockly has achieved many improvements: it allows to create ad-hoc profiles for specific contexts of use, to model weaknesses and vulnerabilities of the system, assessing the risk coming from them; it allows the graphical visualization of attack paths and a fast prototyping through the generation of a java code skeleton; it allows analysing of cascading effect.

Behind the functional improvements there are many technical enhancements which are described herein. From the technical perspective, ResilBlockly has been completely redesigned with regard to Blockly4SoS, selecting cutting-edge technologies suitable for the realization of a system based on the concept of Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA) [20], with particular attention to security, in contrast to the monolithic architecture on which Blockly4SoS was based. In ResilBlockly, service-oriented capabilities are expressed formally with resource-oriented REST (REpresentational State Transfer) APIs that provide the core business logic as-a-service from the backend to the frontend of the application. APIs operate as a loose coupled collection of resources that work together. With this approach, the same service can be reused in more than one business process or over different business channels or digital touchpoints. While the user interface has been developed relying on Angular framework and Typescript language, REST services have been developed in Java and data access has been entrusted to Java Persistence API (JPA) and Hibernate ORM to manages MySQL database integration.

The ResilBlockly backend architecture is composed by four main layers: the controller layer, responsible for publishing the business logic operations as REST services, the manager layer, responsible for the implementation of the core business logic of the application; the service layer, responsible for the integration of the application with third-party services, the model layer, responsible for the integration with the database and provides CRUD operations to the upper layer (Manager layer).

B. Main Functionalities

ResilBlockly is made up by two main components: the *Profile Designer* and the *Model Designer*. In the Profile Designer, the user can create different profiles within the tool, or import them as ecore UML to adapt the modelling to the specific context of use. Each profile can be instantiated in a model within the Model Designer functionality. A screenshot of the Model Designer is in Fig. 1.

The *Risk Assessment* functionality, that is the main improvement respect to Blockly4SoS, comprises several types of analysis: an HAZOP-based analysis of functionalities and interfaces; a modelling and assessment of weaknesses and vulnerabilities of the system; an assessment of risk due to

Fig. 1. The Model Designer of ResilBlockly with a portion of a model of the case study

cascading effects. The HAZOP-based analysis permits to analyse in a systematic way every function and interface existing in the system model. The first step is to identify in the Profile Designer which Class block has to be considered a Function or an Interface. Once that this operation has been performed, the user is only asked to provide two types of inputs to automatically obtain a pre-filled HAZOP report: keywords and templates. The keywords are used to describe the failure to be analysed; they have to be chosen according to the context of use. Some typical HAZOP keywords are NOT, LATE, DENIAL, OTHER THAN. The template permits to create automatically the description of the scenarios combining the keywords with the functions or interfaces inserted in the model. The output of this functionality is an HAZOP sheet, prefilled with the scenarios to be analysed and that can be finalised offline by the user.

The functionality of Risk Assessment includes also the modelling of *Weaknesses* and *Vulnerabilities* and the assessment of risk related with them. In a specific interface, the user can select through a dropdown list a block of the profile or of the model, which, by doing so, is implicitly identified as asset under analysis. Then, weaknesses can be searched into the CWE catalogue [22]: it is possible to find weaknesses, read short descriptions, jump to the CWE catalogue, study the details and finally associate the weakness to the asset. Custom weaknesses can be also defined. In addition, CWE weaknesses can be indirectly searched by looking for CAPEC attack patterns [21]. This can be considered a different approach and starting point for the identification of weaknesses. In similar way to what explained for the weaknesses, the research and association of vulnerabilities from the CVE catalogue [23], or the addition of custom defined ones can be performed as well. For the CWEs and CVEs associated to the assets, the related risk is automatically computed by the tool as soon as Severity and Likelihood are either inserted by the user or automatically

retrieved them from the catalogues, when available. The export of the analysis is possible through CSV files.

V. CASCADING EFFECTS ANALYSIS IN RESILBLOCKLY

This section presents the functionality with which the user can perform the cascading effects analysis through the ResilBlockly tool. Three main sequential activities are foreseen by the cascading effects methodology presented in Section III: definition of asset dependencies; threat analysis; generation of the cascading graph (produced automatically by the tool). Each step is performed in a different tab of Risk Assessment functionality.

A. Asset dependencies

The first step of the methodology involves defining the direct dependencies existing between two different modelled assets. In the “*Dependencies*” tab of Profile Designer, the user chooses a class block representing the *Initiating asset*, two relation blocks – i.e., the *destination* and *dependency* respectively –, and finally the dependency type (to be chosen among [11]: resource, communication, service, interference, and rule). After this propaedeutic operation, in the Model Designer in the “*Asset dependencies*” tab (depicted in Fig. 2), ResilBlockly automatically lists all possible dependencies between the modelled assets. At this stage, the user can complement dependencies data by excluding some entries and add likelihood and impact values for each dependency. The tool automatically shows the associated risk, expressed in a qualitative scale.

B. Threat Analysis

In the “*Threat analysis*” tab, the user should specify potential initiating threats from which the consequent threats are triggered and spread within the system. First, the user selects a threat from a taxonomy including cyber, physical and natural threats. Finally, to conclude this step, likelihood of the threat and impacted assets can be selected.

Initiating asset	Cascading asset	Dependency object	Dependency type	Likelihood	Impact	Dependency risk
Control VM	Control Workstation	Data to Workstation	Communication	High	3	Moderate
Control VM	Firewall	Requested data to User 1	Communication	Very Low	8	Low
Control Workstation	Control VM	Data request to VM	Communication	High	9	High
Firewall	Control VM	Request from User 2	Communication	Moderate	3	Moderate

Fig. 2. Definition of asset dependencies

C. Dependency graph

The “*Dependency graph*” tab allows the user to visualize the graph resulting from the dependencies defined in the previous phases. Once an initiating threat is chosen through the user interface, the tool produces a table of the cascading effects generated by that threat, reporting in each line a path with its related “*Cumulative Dependency Risk*” (CDR) [16]. For each path a CDR is calculated and, since a path can have multiple instances, also an “*Average cumulative dependency risk*” for all instances is given. User can click on a path to open a window with the representation of the path in the form of a tree. By clicking the button “Open Dependency Graph”, the tool generates and shows the complete dependency graph. The “*Combined Common-Cause and Cascading Failure Risk*” [16] is here computed; this value combines the likelihood of each threat with all the possible dependency chains that may be triggered by the threat being realized.

VI. A CASE STUDY: THE 7SHIELD PROJECT

A. The 7SHIELD Project

In the European security landscape, Space ground segments increasingly appear as potential “new targets” of “new threats”, especially the hybrid ones (e.g., cyber-physical). Indeed, a physical/cyber-attack toward the space ground segment installations or communication networks would cause debilitating impact on public safety and security of European citizens, and could also affect other European critical infrastructures through cascading effects.

7SHIELD [24] aims at providing a holistic framework dedicated to the protection of space ground segment infrastructures & assets against hybrid threats by covering all the phases of crisis management, namely pre-crisis, crisis and post-crisis phases. The framework comprises a level of sensors and a level of detectors which detect both cyber and physical attacks, a level of components which perform correlation and combination of information that come from the detector and a level of services for the prevention and the preparedness, for monitoring and early warning and for response and mitigation. In this framework, ResilBlockly belongs to services level, providing services for prevention and preparedness phase.

B. Application to the ground segment of a space system

This section describes an application of the cascading effect feature of ResilBlockly in the 7SHIELD project. In 7SHIELD, a UML Profile ad hoc for ground segment of space systems has been realised within the tool, allowing the modelling of specific assets of the space domain. Thanks to the 7SHIELD Profile, during the project, it has been possible to model the infrastructures of the five pilot use cases. The infrastructure of ground segment of space systems includes elements with telecommunication capabilities to receive or send RF signals, centres to manage satellites data, payload and telemetries, and terrestrial networks which connect the different elements to each other and share data collected with the users [26]. In Fig. 1, on the left side, the menu and the menu items defined in the profile are shown: the figure highlights the Space Ground Segment Assets menu and its menu items. In the middle of the interface there is a white area where the actual model is realized; the figure shows a portion of a model of a generic ground segment of space system, because for security reasons details of pilot infrastructures have to be omitted.

In the following, an application of the analysis of cascading effect is reported. In Fig. 2, the first step with the specification of dependencies is shown. The user interface shows the list of the dependencies automatically retrieved from the model. The user has to add likelihood and impact of each dependency. Some dependencies can be excluded from the analysis clicking on the icon on the left. The tool automatically evaluates the level of risk. In Fig. 2, two dependencies have “Moderate” risk, while the other two have “Low” and “High” risk. The type of the dependencies shown is “Communication” since the assets exchange some messages.

The second step, is the analysis of initiating threats. First, user will select a threat from drop down menu. Here, the user will sequentially select the Category (i.e., Physical, Natural, or Cyber) to which the threat belongs, Type and Threat (Attack strategy). Category, Type and Threat are based on the adopted threat taxonomy. Then, the user selects a likelihood from drop down menu and adds impacted assets. Ground segment of space systems are vulnerable to computer network exploitation attacks that compromise the network to which a ground station is connected to. This type of attack could include exploitation

of poorly configured or vulnerable technologies as well as phishing to gain unauthorized access to ground stations [26].

In the reported case study, the cyber threat “Exploitation of poorly configured technologies (DOS, DDOS, BOTNET)” has been associated with the impacted asset “Firewall”. The likelihood value is “High”. The third step consists in the generation of the dependency graph. Once an initiating threat is chosen from a dropdown menu, the tool produces a table of the cascading effects generated by that threat. In fact, it shows the various existing paths (each path in a distinct line) with their related “Cumulative Dependency Risk”.

Fig. 3. Dependency graph

User can click on a path to see its multiple instances in the form of a tree. Along with the links of tree, information regarding “dependency object”, “dependency type”, likelihood (“LH”) and impact (“IMP”) is presented for a better understanding of user. For each chain, a “cumulative dependency risk” is calculated and an “Average cumulative dependency risk” for all instances is given. By clicking the button “Open Dependency Graph”, the tool generates and shows the complete dependency graph, shown in Fig. 3. The asset from which a threat starts is shown with a lightning bolt symbol (⚡). In the graph nodes, “Firewall” is the initial impacted asset. At the bottom right, a “Combined Common-Cause and Cascading Failure Risk” of 1673.44 is computed.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we presented the adoption of a methodology for the analysis of cascading effects and its implementation in ResilBlockly, a MDE software tool for the modelling and analysis of complex systems and infrastructures. The architecture of the tool and its functionalities have been described, highlighting the improvements respect to the previous version of the tool, called Blockly4SoS. Finally, it is presented the validation of the adopted methodology and of the tool itself with the protection of a space ground segment infrastructure derived from the 7SHIELD European project.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially supported by the H2020 project 7SHIELD Grant Agreement No.883284.

REFERENCES

[1] D. Dudenhoefter, M. Permann, and M. Manic. (2006). CIMS: A Framework for Infrastructure Interdependency Modeling and Analysis. Proceedings - Winter Simulation Conference. 478-485.

[2] Pescaroli, G., & Alexander, D. (2015). A definition of cascading disasters and cascading effects: Going beyond the “toppling dominos” metaphor. *Planet@ risk*, 3(1), 58-67.

[3] Fundamentals of Emergency Management Course - Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA): <https://training.fema.gov/is/courseoverview.aspx?code=IS-230.d>

[4] Rahman, H. A., et al. (2011). Quantitative estimates of critical infrastructures’ interdependencies on the communication and information technology infrastructure. *International journal of critical infrastructures*, 7(3), 220-242.

[5] Goto, Y., et al. (2008). Damage propagation caused by interdependency among critical infrastructures. In *The 14th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering*.

[6] Bigger, J. E., et al. (2009). Consequences of critical infrastructure interdependencies: lessons from the 2004 hurricane season in Florida. *Int. journal of critical infrastructures*, 5(3), 199-219.

[7] Dueñas-Osorio, L., & Kwasinski, A. (2012). Quantification of lifeline system interdependencies after the 27 February 2010 Mw 8.8 offshore Maule, Chile, earthquake. *Earthquake Spectra*, 28(1_suppl1), 581-603.

[8] McDaniels, T., Chang, S., Peterson, K., Mikawoz, J., & Reed, D. (2007). Empirical framework for characterizing infrastructure failure interdependencies. *Journal of Infrastructure Systems*, 13(3), 175-184.

[9] Basu, N., Pryor, R., & Quint, T. (1998). ASPEN: A microsimulation model of the economy. *Computational Economics*, 12(3), 223-241.

[10] Barton, D. C., et al. (2000). Aspen-EE: an agent-based model of infrastructure interdependency. SAND2000-2925. Albuquerque, NM: Sandia National Laboratories.

[11] FORTRESS EU project - Foresight Tools for Responding to cascading effects in a crisis

[12] CascEff EU project - Modelling of dependencies and cascading effects for emergency management in crisis situations

[13] Leontief W. (1936). Quantitative Input and Output Relations in the Economic Systems of the United States. *The Review of Economics and Statistics* 18, no. 3 (1936): 105-25.

[14] Delamare, S., et al. (2009). High-level modelling of critical infrastructures’ interdependencies. *International Journal of Critical Infrastructures*, 5(1-2), 100-119.

[15] Bobbio, A., et al. (2010). Unavailability of critical SCADA communication links interconnecting a power grid and a Telco network. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 95(12), 1345-1357.

[16] Kotzanikolaou, P., et al. (2013, March). Cascading effects of common-cause failures in critical infrastructures. In *Int. Conf. on Critical Infrastructure Protection* (pp. 171-182). Springer.

[17] Stergiopoulos, G., et al. (2017). A process-based dependency risk analysis methodology for critical infrastructures. *Int. J. of Critical Infrastructures*, 13(2-3), 184-205.

[18] Stergiopoulos, G., et al. (2020). Automatic network restructuring and risk mitigation through business process asset dependency analysis. *Computers & Security*, 96, 101869.

[19] AMADEOS EU FP7-ICT-2013.3.4 Project: Architecture for Multi-criticality Agile Dependable Evolutionary Open System-of-Systems <http://amadeos-project.eu/>. GA no. 610535.

[20] M Endrei et al, “Patterns: ServiceOriented Architecture and Web Services”. IBM WebSphereSoftware 2004.

[21] CAPEC, “Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification”. <https://capec.mitre.org/index.html>

[22] CWE Common Weakness Enumeration. <https://cwe.mitre.org/>

[23] CVE Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures <https://cve.mitre.org/>

[24] 7SHIELD EU H2020 Project - <https://www.7shield.eu/project/> Grant Agreement No.883284 Ross, R. S. (2012).

[25] NIST SP 800-30 Rev. 1: Guide for Conducting Risk Assessments. [online], <https://csrc.nist.gov/publications/detail/sp/800-30/rev-1/final>

[26] Manulis, M., Bridges, C. P., Harrison, R., Sekar, V., & Davis, A. (2021). Cyber security in new space. *International Journal of Information Security*, 20(3), 287-311. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10207-020-00503-w>